

Numerical analysis to evaluate the structural performance of NFRCM (Natural Fabric-Reinforced Cementitious) strengthened masonry

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Abstract. The innovative sustainable technology based on natural fabric-reinforced cementitious matrix (NFRCM) is analyzed for strengthening masonry. A new frontier for composite materials is proposed as an alternative to well-known traditional technologies used to improve the seismic behavior of buildings, such as the portuguese technique ‘gaiola pombalina’, the Italian ‘baraccata house’ and the turkish ‘himis house’. Preliminary sensitivity analysis is performed on NFRCM and ‘baraccata’ numerical models. Both technologies are numerically compared. From the experimental results of in-plane incremental load test carried out by CNR-Ivalsa a numerical model is calibrated by non-linear pushover analysis to evaluate the behavior of masonry wall strengthened with natural fibers. This paper demonstrates the effectiveness of NFRCM systems for strengthening masonry as: i) a non-invasive solution without significant thickness; ii) a sustainable technology; iii) an intervention involving the whole wall surface avoiding failure local mechanisms.

Introduction

In the field of masonry built heritage preservation, the more common solutions for strengthening interventions are fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) composites and fiber reinforced cementitious matrices (FRCM) [1,2]. The fiber materials commonly used are carbon, glass, steel, aramid, which come from non-renewable sources and some of them are synthetic materials. Focusing on sustainable solutions, natural fibers have actually replaced metal or ceramic-based materials in several applications for the automotive, aerospace, electronics and construction industries [3,4]. Due to these promising aspects, natural fiber reinforced cementitious matrix (NFRCM) strengthening systems for masonry have been recently taken into considerations by means of laboratory testing and numerical modelling of small specimens [5-7].

It is worth mentioning that in the past, after seismic events of considerable intensity, several pre-modern, anti-seismic devices based on timber frames and masonry walls collaboration were proposed in Mediterranean basin countries (Portuguese ‘Gaiola Pombalina’, Turkish ‘Himis’ system, Italian Bourbon ‘baraccata’ house [8,9]). This solution represented and still represents a sustainable strengthening technology that is embedded into existing masonry structural elements and is not added as an external reinforcement; however, it can be re-thought in a modern way as a further sustainable solution. **The static and dynamic benefits of this technology are given combining the compressive strength of masonry to tensile strength of wood. The strut and tie behavior assured by wood frame strengthened by infill masonry improves the response to horizontal loads.**

This contribution is dedicated to the numerical investigation of the structural performance of sustainable masonry strengthening solutions, with particular attention to NFRCM and ‘baraccata’ systems. For this purpose, an existing case study, taken from an experimental laboratory campaign on a ‘baraccata’ masonry panel subjected to in-plane loads [10] is assumed as reference and reproduced by a standard three-dimensional Finite Element Model (3D FEM). Then, a NFRCM

strengthening intervention is proposed on the same unreinforced masonry panel numerical tests are carried out on the calibrated models. A sensitivity analysis is performed in order to compare the behavior of sustainable strengthening systems and to highlight the main advantages of the NFRCM solution. Furthermore, the numerical tests aim to show capability of the proposed tools in representing the structural behavior of strengthened masonry.

Numerical models

‘Baraccata’ Masonry Finite Element Model. The first model is based on CNR-IVALSA laboratory experimental research on a ‘baraccata’ masonry panel subjected to in-plane loads (Fig. 1) [10].

In particular, a ‘Baraccata’ wall (width 339 cm, height 283 cm, thick 41 cm) with a window in the centre of the façade (width 88 cm, height 152 cm) was tested combining a vertical constant load (18.7 kN/m) and cyclic horizontal load (Fig. 1 a and b). Fig. 1c shows the hysteretic behaviour of wall highlighting the loss of strength and deformative capacity.

Fig. 1 – CNR-Ivalsa experimental test: (a) wall scheme with load and boundary conditions; (b) ‘baraccata’ wall; (c) load-displacement curve.

3D FEM of the wall is defined and calibrated on the mentioned experimental results [10]. Details of 3D FEM, made of 8-nodes brick elements, are showed in Fig. 2, while the mechanical properties assumed for the materials are listed in the first two rows of Tab. 1. Nodal vertical and horizontal displacements at the base of the model were fixed.

Fig. 2 –FE model: load and boundary conditions

Tab. 1 –FE model: material physical and mechanical properties

Materials	Elastic Modulus [MPa]	Poisson ratio	Density [kg/m ³]	Friction angle [deg]	Cohesion [MPa]	Failure criterion
Masonry	6.9×10^2	0.24	1900	30°	1.5×10^{-1}	Mohr Coulomb
Wood	5×10^2	0.4	600	-	-	-
NFRCM [6]	1.5×10^4	0.2	1800	-	-	-

NFRCM Masonry Finite Element Model. Based on ‘baraccata’ masonry FEM calibrated with experimental results, another numerical model is proposed considering NFRCM instead of ‘baraccata’ technology as strengthening system for further parametrical analysis (Fig. 3a). Both geometrical and mechanical parameters considered for NFRCM reinforcement were formulated by authors in a previous work [6]. Mechanical properties assumed in the FEM are collected in the third row of Tab. 1.

NFRCM is constituted by a hydraulic lime mortar and one layer of Sisal plain-woven textile made of 10x10 mm² sisal yarns mesh. The NFRCM with thickness of 10 mm is considered applied on both masonry panels surfaces. The characterization of NFRCM constituent materials was performed by authors in a previous work [7] allowing to establish their composite mechanical behavior. A perfect adhesion between NFRCM and masonry panel was considered in model in agreement with experimental results obtained previously [11].

In order to evaluate the structural behavior of masonry without reinforcements, a further FEM considering unreinforced masonry panel is studied (Fig. 3b).

Sensitivity analysis: NFRCM versus ‘baraccata’

Parametric analyses with NFRCM, ‘baraccata’ and unreinforced masonry finite element models are performed, based on their linear and nonlinear behavior. In-plane behavior of both NFRCM and ‘baraccata’ techniques are compared to evaluate the improvement on shear response of each strengthening system by reference to unreinforced masonry characteristics.

Fig. 3 – Boundary conditions of FEMs for parametric analyses: (a) masonry and NFRCM; (b) unreinforced masonry wall

Linear behavior. NFRCM and ‘baraccata’ systems are compared. Numerical analysis evidences that for NFRCM by reference to ‘baraccata’ technology presents a better mechanical behavior as higher stiffness and lower tension in masonry layer. Furthermore, results in terms of in-plane stresses show that tension state decreases in masonry layer and consequently the stress state in masonry becomes almost homogeneous (Figs. 4 and 5).

Fig. 4 – Vertical stresses with 18.7 kN/m vertical load and 100 kN horizontal load: (a) ‘baraccata’ masonry; (b) unreinforced masonry (c) NFRCM masonry

Fig. 5 – Horizontal stresses with 18.7 kN/m vertical load and 100 kN horizontal load: (a) ‘baraccata’ masonry; (b) unreinforced masonry (c) NFRCM masonry

As highlighted by Figs. 4c and 5c the stresses concentration reaches high values both for vertical and horizontal directions (Z and X-direction respectively) thanks to the contribute of NFRCM layer which relieves the work of masonry panel (Figs. 4b and 5b).

Nonlinear behavior. In a second step, in-plane nonlinear pushover analysis is carried out to assess the seismic capacity of NFRCM solution by reference to ‘baraccata’ technology.

Plot results (Fig. 6) compare the load-displacement relationships of masonry panel (curve a) with masonry strengthened by different reinforcement types, ‘baraccata’ (curve b) and NFRCM (curve c). Results evidence that the maximum strength on masonry panel increases both on ‘baraccata’ and NFRCM solutions. Stiffness increment with ‘baraccata’ technology is 23% by reference to unreinforced masonry wall. NFRCM improvement is higher than ‘baraccata’, presenting an increment about 33%. In addition, the ductility increment is higher in NFRCM masonry. Further analyses considering fracture energy parameters on materials would establish the amount of **deformative capacity** increment on NFRCM masonry panels.

Fig.6 – Nonlinear in-plane analysis results: Load-displacement curves

Conclusions and remarks

In this work, the scope is to demonstrate the structural contribute of natural fabric-reinforced cementitious matrix technology (NFRCM-strengthened masonry) on improving the seismic capacity of historical masonry structures. Parametric analysis with NFRCM system is performed, starting from an experimental research carried out on a wall built by ‘baraccata’ technology. In-plane behavior of both NFRCM and ‘baraccata’ techniques are compared. First results evidence NFRCM technology advantages, as relieving the stress generated in masonry walls and a homogeneous stress distribution. **An increment of deformative capacity is assured by NFRCM solution comparable with ‘baraccata’ technology than masonry panel.**

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References

- [1] A. Nanni. FRCC strengthening – a new tool in the concrete and masonry repair toolbox. *Concr Int Des Constr* 34(4) (2012) 43–9.
- [2] G. De Felice, S. De Santis, L. Garmendia, B. Ghiassi, P. Larrinaga, P.B. Lourenco, D.V. Oliveira, F. Paolacci, G.C. Papanicolaou, Mortar-based systems for externally bonded strengthening of masonry, *Mater and Struct* 47 (2014) 2021-2037.
- [3] T. Gurunathan, S. Mohanty, S.K.A. Nayak, Review of the recent developments in biocomposites based on natural fibres and their application perspectives, *Compos. A Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 77 (2015) 1–25.
- [4] K. Begum, M.A. Islam, Natural fiber as a substitute to synthetic fiber in polymer composites: a review. *Res. J. Eng. Sci.* 2 (3) (2013) 46–53.
- [5] C.B. De Carvalho Bello, A. Cecchi, E. Meroi, D.V. Oliveira. Experimental and Numerical Investigations on the Behaviour of Masonry Walls Reinforced with an Innovative Sisal FRCC System. *Key Engineering Materials* 747 (2017) 190-195.
- [6] C.B. De Carvalho Bello, D. Baraldi, G. Boscato, A., Cecchi, O., Mazzarella, E., Meroi, I., Aldreggetti, G., Costantini, L., Massaria, V. Scafuri, I. Tofani, Numerical and theoretical models for NFRCM-strengthened masonry. I. *Key Engineering Materials* 817 (2019) 44–49.
- [7] C.B. De Carvalho Bello, I. Boem, N. Gattesco, A. Cecchi, D.V. Oliveira. Experimental tests for the characterization of sisal fiber reinforced cementitious matrix for strengthening masonry structures. *Construction and Building Materials* 219 (2019) 44–55.
- [8] H. Cruz, J. Saporiti Machado, A., Campos Costa, P., Xavier Candeias, N., Ruggieri, J., Manuel Catarino. Historical Earthquake-Resistant Timber Framing in the Mediterranean Area, *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering*, vol. 1, Springer (2016).
- [9] A. Dutu, H. Sakata, Y. Yamazaki, T. Shindo. In-Plane behavior of timber frames with masonry infills under static cyclic loading. *Journal of Structural Engineering* 142 (2) (2016).
- [10] N. Ruggieri. *L'ingegneria antisismica nel Regno di Napoli (1734-1799)*. Roma: Aracne. (2015).
- [11] C.B. de Carvalho Bello, D. Baraldi, A. Cecchi, D.V. Oliveira, Experimental Characterization of Masonry Panels Strengthened with NFRCM, *Key Eng. Mater.* 898 (2021) 43-48.